

MOTIVATION AND ATTENTION PHENOMENA: AN ANALYSIS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract. *This article analyzes theoretical approaches to the psychological phenomena of motivation and attention, which are central components of human mental activity. It explores how motivation influences human behavior and how attention interrelates with mental processes. The interaction between these two phenomena is examined through the lens of scientific perspectives. The study compares classical and modern psychological schools of thought and highlights their relevance in applied psychology.*

Keywords: *motivation, learning activity, interest, attention stability, distribution, mobility, attention, focused attention.*

Introduction

In the complex structure of human mental life, the phenomena of motivation and attention occupy a distinct place. While motives are internal factors that drive a person's activity, attention plays a crucial role in directing that activity toward a specific goal. In psychology, although these concepts are studied separately, they are in fact closely interconnected. Motivational processes stimulate individuals, while attention governs their conscious activities. The quality of attention largely depends on the strength of motives formed within an individual. Positively developed motives serve as the foundation for the effectiveness of attention and other psychological processes. This article delves into the study of the problem of motivation, which is intrinsically linked to the significance of attention, and discusses its scientific relevance.

The topic of motivation has been one of the most extensively studied problems in the history of psychology. Scholars from around the world have approached it from various perspectives. As a result of their research, numerous scientific schools emerged, each offering distinct conceptualizations of the nature and role of motivation. Below we briefly review these perspectives.

Representatives of Russian and Soviet psychology—including K.D. Ushinsky, I.M. Sechenov, I.P. Pavlov, V.M. Bekhterev, A.F. Lazursky, V.N. Myasishchev, A.A. Ukhtomsky, D.N. Uznadze, S.L. Rubinstein, A.N. Leontiev, P.M. Yakobson, V.S. Merlin, L.I. Bozhovich, V.I. Selivanov, V.G. Aseev, and others – have made significant contributions to the study of motivation. Today, dozens of scientific theories of motivation exist [1, p. 209].

In Uzbekistan, the problem of academic motivation has also been widely investigated by local researchers. Currently, motivation is interpreted in psychology in different ways. According to V.G. Aseev, in one interpretation, it is seen as a set of factors that direct and support behavior [5, p. 48]. In another, it is viewed as a collection of motives, and in yet another, as a force that activates and drives behavior by determining its direction.

The term *motivation* was first used by A. Schopenhauer in his essay *The Fourfold Root of the Principle of Sufficient Reason* (1900–1910). Later, the term was firmly established in psychological discourse to explain the causes of human and animal behavior.

According to I.A. Djidaryan, motivation is the driving force that fuels a person's activity in life and work. It is based on motives, which in turn are specific internal impulses that encourage and activate behavior. When discussing student motivation, it is understood as the set of methods and processes that stimulate interest in learning and facilitate effective assimilation of educational content. Furthermore, motivation is seen as a psychological regulatory mechanism, encompassing the process of motive activation and the emergence of behavioral patterns. It functions as a system of impulses and responses to activity [2, p. 199].

Methodology

In psychology, a *motive* is a factor that prompts a person to pursue a specific goal. It is considered an internal driving force that emerges as a higher form of need. Needs, instincts, desires, emotions, and ideals all fall under the category of motives. In modern psychology, the term *motive* refers to various phenomena and conditions that activate the subject. A set of motives guiding a person's behavior is called *motivation*. A motive originates from and is shaped by needs. The stability of a need contributes to the effective formation of motivation. Since action is a component of activity, it is governed by both its purpose and motive. The terms *emotion*, *goal*, and *attitude* are sometimes used interchangeably with *motive*, and it is often equated with concepts like impulse, drive, and stimulus. Motivation plays a vital role in the process of personal self-development, helping individuals think more clearly and purposefully.

R.A. Rudik notes that motive pairs such as emotion–aspiration, interest–need, and ideals–attitudes can function as motivational structures. Therefore, motives are part of a complex dynamic system that includes decision-making, evaluation, and analysis of choices made [1, p. 112].

Based on these definitions, motivation can be classified into two main approaches. The first considers motivation from a systematic perspective—as a set of motives or influencing factors.

In his scientific research, A.A. Fayzullaev identified and analyzed various factors of a person's motivation for self-regulation. These factors relate to the characteristics of personal motivation, the methods of implementing motivational regulation, and their outcomes. Furthermore, his works outline the objectification of motivational structures by the individual, as well as different psychological strategies and methods of motivational regulation. The study also examines motivation as it relates to various areas of self-regulation in a person's life activities. A.A. Fayzullaev proposed a step-by-step analysis of the motivational process, dividing it into five stages:

The first stage is the emergence and awareness of arousal. Complete awareness of arousal is defined as understanding what object has triggered the arousal and comprehending the methods and results of carrying out the related action. According to the author, the awareness of arousal can be seen in needs, inclinations, aspirations, and, more broadly, any psychological phenomena.

The second stage is called the acceptance of the motive. The author explains this as the internal acceptance of arousal. At this stage, a person analyzes their moral principles, values, and other factors, deciding how important the arising need or inclination is for their life and whether it should be satisfied.

The third stage is the implementation of the motive. During this process, depending on specific circumstances and the execution of the motive, its psychological content may change.

The fourth stage is the consolidation of the motive, where the motive transforms into a characteristic feature.

The fifth stage is the potential activation of arousal, where a certain feature of character emerges either consciously or unconsciously.

Fayzullaev's approach to dividing the motivational process into stages facilitates psychological analysis and, to some extent, enhances the ability to regulate this process.

In psychological literature, scholars who study the theory of attention define it as the focusing and concentration of mental activity on a specific object. Researchers exploring the theoretical significance of attention have studied its relationship with other mental processes and its role in mental activity from various perspectives.

Results and discussion

The problems of attention and its connection to other mental processes, as well as its role, have been studied by scientists such as N.N. Lange, A.R. Luria, and others. For example, Russian psychologist N.N. Lange describes the connection of attention with volitional, reflexive, instinctive, and perceptual states in his work "The Theory of Volitional Attention." According to A.R. Luria, it is easier to observe attention in young children. At the first stage, due to instability and narrow scope, the child cannot divide attention among multiple stimuli because the reflexes associated with new stimuli at early or preschool age are weak.

Regarding the role of attention in human activity, French scientist Cuvier defines talent as sustained attention. From this definition, the importance of volitional attention in achieving the level of talent becomes clear. In this process, the quality of working attentively, i.e., concentrated attention, plays a key role.

The scientific significance of concentrated attention was studied by Russian psychologist P.P. Blonsky, whose fundamental idea is that attention is directed at a single object. This scientific model is expressed as consciousness being object-oriented. Blonsky argued, "Once a person's consciousness is focused on one object, they do not notice surrounding things and events."

The issue of attention has also been extensively studied by scholars in our country. In particular, Davletshin links the conditions of attention's stability and intensity to the following factors:

1. The state of the nervous system;
2. The content of the object;
3. The content of the activity;
4. The conditions under which the activity is performed;
5. The manifestation of emotions;
6. Reliance on willpower;
7. Conditions;
8. Interest.

These factors determine how effectively a person can perform a task based on the condition of their nervous system (i.e., mood), the meaningfulness of the object to which attention is directed, the attractiveness of the process for the individual, the convenience of the conditions, the pleasure derived from performing the task, the mobilization of volitional qualities, and the degree of the person's interest.

M.E. Zufarova studied the readiness for learning of first-grade students in connection with their developed interest, skills, attention, voluntary memory, voluntary thinking, and speech. Her research revealed that the attention of first-grade students is not sufficiently stable.

M.V. Khalimova, in her study "Attention Deficiency Syndrome in Children and Methods of Its Psychological Correction," found that children with attention deficit syndrome and

hyperactivity show significantly weaker indicators of attention stability and efficiency compared to their healthy peers. This results in faster fatigue during intellectual tasks and more frequent mistakes.

N.S. Abdullayeva, in her research "Psychological Characteristics of Attention Development in Primary School Students," identified gender differences in attention distribution and shifting, as well as differential expressions of internal and external learning motivation. She studied the development of attention stability, distribution, and shifting alongside characteristics such as sociability, mobility, initiative, and emotional stability.

Conclusion

The above analysis shows that the phenomena of motive and attention are integral psychological processes in the regulation of conscious activity. Although different psychological schools interpret these phenomena differently, their central role in all approaches confirms their universal nature and practical importance. Modern psychology views the integrated study of motivational systems and attention processes as an effective approach. Understanding these phenomena is important not only theoretically but also in applied psychological fields such as education, career guidance, and therapy.

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